

INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: The article reveals the specific features of the continuous education system. Activities of higher education institutions operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan were analyzed. During the period from the beginning of the 20th century to the present day, the development process of higher education in Uzbekistan was divided into two stages. Proposals and practical recommendations for increasing the importance of higher education today have been developed.

Keywords: continuing education, higher education, university, academy, institute, specialist, undergraduate, graduate.

The reforms carried out in the education system of our country in the following years are showing their bright results. That is, the system of measures taken to further improve the continuous education system, develop the policy of training qualified personnel, and strengthen the material and technical base of education is bearing fruit. In 2016, in addition to the political-legal, economic, and spiritual spheres, deep quality changes took place in the social sphere as well. During the years of independence, the volume of spending on the social sphere in our republic increased 5 times. Every year, about 60 percent of the state budget is directed to the implementation of tasks in the fields of health care, education, communal economy, and social protection of the population. One of the most important components of the social sphere of the society is the sphere of education, which directly affects the political, legal, economic and spiritual spheres and determines the normative nature and level of maturity of the social spheres.

Speaking about the education system, it is permissible to dwell on the concept of education first of all. Education is the study of elements of nature and society on the basis of standards strictly established by the state, and it is an educational process aimed at a specific goal in the interests of the individual, society and the state.

Education should be focused on the full development of the human personality and strengthening of respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms. Education should promote mutual understanding, goodwill and friendship among all peoples, racial and religious groups and contribute to the peacekeeping activities of the United Nations. Parents have a preferential right to choose the type of education for their children."

The leading resource of any country is people. If a person has the necessary education to find his place in the labor market, to earn enough money to provide himself and his family with a decent life, then he first develops, then his family and the state.

While solving one or another issue of the country's socio-economic development, the state at the same time directs the education system in such a way that it supports education through the changes taking place in the country (re-profiling the economic system, solving the employment problem, improving the legal culture of the population, etc.). political, material-economic, legal, organizational) provides.

Higher education. Higher education provides training of highly qualified specialists. Training of highly educated specialists is carried out in higher educational institutions (universities, academies, institutes and other educational institutions of higher education) on the basis of secondary special, professional education (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Types of higher education institutions operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan ¹

Higher education has two levels: bachelor's and master's degrees, which are evidenced by documents on higher education of the state-approved model.

A bachelor's degree is a basic higher education that provides fundamental and practical knowledge in the field of specialization and lasts at least four years.

A master's degree is a higher education that provides fundamental and practical knowledge in a specific specialty and lasts at least two years on the basis of a bachelor's degree. Citizens have the right to receive second and subsequent higher education on the basis of a contract.

Post-graduate education. Post-university education is aimed at meeting the society's needs for highly qualified scientific and pedagogical personnel and satisfying the individual's creative educational and professional interests. Post-graduate education can be obtained in higher educational institutions and

¹ Кадрлар тайёрлаш миллий дастури. – Т.: Шарқ, 2001. – Б. 32-33.

research institutions (in the form of senior researcher-researcher, independent research).

Training of scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel, scientific degrees and the procedure for awarding titles is determined by law.

It is appropriate to study and analyze the development process of higher education in Uzbekistan from the beginning of the 20th century to the present, dividing it into two stages, and to highlight their specific features.

The first stage covers the period from the beginning of the 20th century to the years of independence, and provides information on the establishment of higher education institutions in the territory of our country during the former union.

Since the 1930s, institutes in the field of pedagogy and teacher training have been established in a number of cities of Uzbekistan. They have become major centers for training teachers for primary and secondary schools and personnel for research institutions. In the 1970s, there were 16 higher education institutions in Uzbekistan. In particular, Kokan (1929), Fergana (1930), Bukhara (1930), Tashkent (1935), Khorezm (1935), Karshi (1936), Namangan (1942), Andijan (1953), Termiz (1965), Syrdarya (1966), Samarkand (1967), Tashkent region (1967), Jizzakh (1974) state pedagogy and Tashkent state foreign languages (1948), Russian language and literature of the Republic (1963)) institutes were established.²

The development of higher technical education in Central Asia began in 1920 with the establishment of the technical faculty of the Turkestan State University. In 1922, 436 students studied at the mechanical, hydrotechnical and mining departments of the technical faculty of the university. In 1923, this faculty was transformed into an engineering-reclamation faculty. On the basis of this faculty, in 1929, the Central Asian Cotton Cultivation and Irrigation Institute, which included 5 faculties, was established. After that, Tashkent railway engineers (1931), Tashkent textiles

and light industry (1932), Tashkent polytechnic (1933), Tashkent communication and electrical engineering (1955), Samarkand cooperative (1961), Tashkent national economy (1962), Samarkand architecture and construction (1966), Fergana polytechnic (1967)), Tashkent highways (1972), Samarkand agriculture (1929), Tashkent agriculture (1934), Tashkent irrigation and mechanization of agriculture (1934), Andijan cotton (1964) institutes began to operate.³

In addition, higher education institutions in the fields of medicine, culture and art were established during that period.

The first paramedic school was established in Tashkent in 1918, and in 1919 it became a higher medical school, and a year later, it functioned as a medical faculty of the Turkestan State University. In 1931, the Central Asian Medical Institute was established on the basis of this faculty, and in 1935, it was named the Tashkent Medical Institute. Samarkand State Medical Institute was founded in 1935 on the basis of the Faculty of Medicine of Uzbekistan State University.

In 1937, the Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, considered the only one in Central Asia, was established on the basis of the Tashkent Medical Institute. After that, in 1955, Andijan and in 1972, the Central Asian pediatric medical institutes started their activities. Tashkent State Conservatory was established in 1936, Tashkent Theater and Art Institute in 1945, Uzbekistan State Institute of Physical Education in 1955, Tashkent State Institute of Culture in 1974.

As can be seen from the above mentioned information, although the first foundations of higher education were laid before the independence of our country, in our opinion, there was no clear system of training qualified specialists for real sectors of the economy.

The second stage covers issues related to the modernization of higher education during the period from the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the present day.

In the early years of independence, special attention was paid to the reform of the higher education system and a number of important tasks were carried out.

First, Andijan, Bukhara, Gulistan, Karshi, Namangan, Fergana, Termiz, Urganch state universities

² Абдурахманов Г.А. Высшая школа Советского Узбекистана. – Ташкент: Укитувчи, 1977. – С. 13-14.

³ Абдурахманов Г.А. Высшая школа Советского Узбекистана. – Ташкент: Укитувчи, 1977. – С. 29-45.

were established on the basis of Tashkent State Technical University, Tashkent State University of Economics, University of World Economy and Diplomacy, Tashkent Islamic University, and relevant pedagogical institutes in the regions. Tashkent Institute of Foreign Languages, Tashkent Agricultural Institute and Tashkent Institute of Communication were also granted university status.

Secondly, in addition to the Tashkent State Technical University, which was registered on the basis of the large Tashkent Polytechnic Institute, two more - Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology and Tashkent Institute of Architecture and Construction were established. The faculties of oriental studies and law were separated from Tashkent State University and transformed into independent Tashkent state institutes of oriental studies and law.

Thirdly, higher education institutions were established in all regions in order to eliminate the shortcomings in the placement of higher education institutions. Because three-quarters of them were located in several large cities, and the main part was located in Tashkent. These are Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, Karshi Engineering-Economic Institute, Namangan Engineering-Economic Institute (at the same time Namangan Engineering-Technology Institute), Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, established on the basis of the above-mentioned 8 regional universities and branches of higher education institutions in Tashkent. It was determined that each higher education institution will operate on the basis of a specific program for restructuring the form and content of education according to the new status.

It is worth noting that, with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to strengthen the material and technical base of higher education institutions and fundamentally improve the quality of training of highly qualified specialists" regarding the improvement of the quality of training of specialists with higher education required in the fields and sectors of the economy, Andijan engineering- Institute of Economics - Andijan Mechanical Engineering Institute; Namangan Engineering-Economic Institute - Namangan Engineering-Technology Institute; Bukhara Institute of Food and Light Industry Technology was transformed into Bukhara High-tech Engineering-Technical Institute (later Bukhara Institute of Engineering-Technology), their specialization was changed and reorganized.

In the future, the scale of establishing branches of large higher education institutions of foreign countries in our country is expanding. International Westminster University was established in Tashkent at the invitation of the Umid Foundation, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, the British Council, and the University of Westminster (UK). The main mission of the International University of Westminster is to train specialists in the fields of "Economy", "Management", "Information Technologies" and "Law" in the bachelor and master's system.

In general, special attention is paid to the issue of training competitive mature personnel in our country, and we fully admit that our national personnel who are being trained today are emerging as personnel who can easily compare with graduates who studied in higher educational institutions of developed foreign countries, and can even show better results than them.

The purpose of higher education, taking into account the future development of the country, is to train highly qualified and competitive personnel capable of high spiritual and educational qualities, the ability to think independently, and to ensure the scientific-technical, socio-economic and cultural development of society. Admission of students to higher education institutions is carried out on the basis of state grants and on a fee-contractual basis.

State and non-state higher education institutions that implement educational programs of higher education courses and specialties in accordance with state educational standards, scientific and pedagogical institutions that carry out research work necessary for the development of higher education, and competent state agencies for education management, as well as enterprises, institutions and organizations under their control. includes

During the past period, as a result of reforms in higher education institutions, the regulatory legal framework of personnel training was completely renewed, it was harmonized with the requirements of the socio-economic development of our country, the improved state education standards were put into

practice, the concept of creating a new generation of educational literature was implemented, modern educational literature was created, material - is manifested through the strengthening of the technical base and the implementation of a number of other measures.

In order to ensure the continuity and integrity of education, recommendations were developed on the basis of a comparative analysis of the subjects and curricula of general secondary, secondary special, vocational education and continuing in higher education, as well as subjects and curricula of undergraduate majors and master's specialties.

In accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the further improvement of the system of post-secondary education" of 2017 No. 4958, starting from July 1, 2017, post-secondary post-secondary education is a two-step (PhD) doctoral course, candidate of science (Doctor science) Doctorate system was introduced. In order to improve the implementation of this system and increase its transparency, the role of scientific councils has been strengthened. As a result, in accordance with international standards, post-secondary education was abolished from one level, switched to a two-level system, and the financing system was changed.

Taking these factors into account, further improvement of the system of training and certification of highly qualified scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel, radical reform of the post-university education system, taking into account advanced world experience and international standards of certification of scientific personnel, as well as the quality of dissertation research, in order to increase its scientific and practical importance, to create conditions for the creative and intellectual potential of young people, this decree of the head of our state was adopted and this direction was fundamentally reformed.

In conclusion, it is appropriate to determine and implement specific measures to increase the scientific potential of professors and teachers, to rejuvenate those with scientific degrees.

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